

IMPORTANT CLASSIFICATION OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY**Khafizova Mukharram Nematillaevna**

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Abstract. *This article provides examples of lexical and grammatical features of the word-formation-suffix, which forms various meanings in the Latin language. Terms with this suffix are a minority in medical terminology. These suffixes are added to the root of the word and have different meanings. Latin has suffixes forming nouns and suffixes forming adjectives, knowledge of suffixes forming a word or meaning is important for easy compilation and translation of medical terms.*

Keywords: *root, suffixes, noun, adjective, verb, elements, terms.*

ВАЖНАЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. *В статье приводятся примеры лексических и грамматических особенностей словообразовательного суффикса, который образует различные значения в латинском языке. Термины с этим суффиксом составляют меньшинство в медицинской терминологии. Эти суффиксы добавляются к корню слова и имеют различные значения. В латыни есть суффиксы, образующие существительные, и суффиксы, образующие прилагательные, знание суффиксов, образующих слово или значение, важно для легкого составления и перевода медицинских терминов.*

Ключевые слова: *корень, суффиксы, существительное, прилагательное, глагол, элементы, термины.*

Introduction. Medical terminology, like the term system of any other science, is a plurality of interconnected elements that represent a stable unity with specific properties and patterns. There is still no single classification of medical terms. In Latin, suffixes are widely used in the creation of medical, anatomical and clinical terms. Suffixes are endings that are not used independently, but serve to express various meanings related to lexical and grammatical properties, joining the roof. The derived base obtained in this way is called suffixes. Suffixes serve as an important classification. As a word-formation basis, various categories of words are used in suffixation - noun, adjective and verb. Some suffixes are added only with the root of a certain number of words: For example, suffixes **al**, **- ar** with the root of a noun; suffixes **-io**, **-or** with the root of a verb. The addition of a suffix starting with a consonant letter to the root of the word occurs through an auxiliary vowel. This is called an interference.

Latin words usually come with the vowel- **i** - and in words borrowed from greek with **-o**.

For example, lat. cruc-**i**-formis - cruciform; tuberos – **i**-tas- tuberosity; greek. bronch-**o**-genus - bronchogenic, etc.

When forming adjectives, the suffix is attached to the root of the noun, in which it is in the form of the genitive singular. For example: larynx, ngis – laryng-**e**-us; margo, inis - margin-**al**-is; cartilago, inis – cartilagin-**e**-us; occiput, itis – occipit-**al**-is etc.

Materials and methods. Suffixes are used to give meaning to different roots. Roots, suffixes often come from Greek and Latin. Terms with broad meanings are created using word-formation elements. Below we will look at the suffixes that are added to the root of the word and create new meanings.

I. Nouns formed by a suffix meaning diminutive meanings: 1) **-ul**, for example: lobus, lob-**ulus** – lobe, lobule; vena, ven-**ula**- vein, venule; lingua, ling-**ula** - tongue, tongue; frenum, fren-**ulum** – bridle; caput, capit-**ulum** - head; tuba, tub-**ulus** - tube, tubule; nodus, nod-**ulus**-node, nodule, globus, glob-**ulus** - globe; membrana, membran-**ula** -membrane, membranule; glomus, glomer-**ulum** – tangle; vesica, vesic-**ula** – bladder, vesicle; ductus, duct-**ulus** - duct; fossa, foss-**ula** - pit, dimple; ramus, ram-**ulus** – branch of nerve; valva, valv-**ula** – valve; zona, zon-**ula** – belt; saccus, sacc-**ulus** – sac;

2) **-cul**, canalis, canali-**culus**- canal, canaliculus; os, ossi-**culum**-bone; auris, auri – **cula**-ear; cutis, cuti-**cula**-skin, cuticle; tuber, tuber-**culum**- tubercle; venter, ventri -**culus**- stomach, ventricle; genu, geni - **culum**- knee; radix, radi – **cula**- root, radical; corpus, corpus-**culum**-body, corpuscle; dens, denti-**culus** – tooth, denticle; vas, vas-**culum**- vessel, small vessel;

3) **-ol**, area, are-**ola**- area, areola; bronchus, bronchi-**olus**- bronchus, bronchiole; arteria, arteri-**ola**- artery, arteriole; fovea, fove-**ola** - pit, dimple;

4) **-ell**, cerebrum, cereb-**ellum** - brain, cerebellum; lamina, lam-**ella**- lamella;

5) **-ill**, mamma, mamm – **illa**- mammary gland, mamilla;

II. Suffixes of nouns from a verb expressing the meaning of an action, process:

1) **-io** (*tio, sio, xio*) flexum, flex-**io**- to flex, flexion. In Latin, such nouns denote operations, methods of examination, treatment, and physiological functions. For example: operatum, operat-**io**-to operate, operation, surgical intervention; palpatum, palpat-**io**- to palpate, palpation; emotum, emot-**io**- to feel, emotion, feeling; curatum, curat-**io**- to treat, treatment; lectum, lect-**io**-lecture; auscultatum, auscultat-**io**- auscultation, hearing; percussum, percuss-**io**-percussion, knocking, respiratum, respirat-**io** – respiration, breathing; transfusum, transfus-**io** - blood transfusion; agglutinatum, agglutinatio – agglutination and etc.

2) **-or** (*tor, sor, xor*) constrictum, musculus constrict-**or** - constrict, constrictive muscle; depressum, m. depress-**or** - lower, sinking muscle; excavatum, excavat-**or** –excavate, excavator; extensum, m. extens-**or** – extension, extensor muscle; tensum, m. tens-**or**- to strain, a straining

muscle; curatum, curat-**or** – to take care, curator, supervisor; supinatum, supinator – supinator; repetetum, repetit-**or** -to repeat, tutor. Such nouns denote an object, an instrument, and activities in various fields.

III. Nouns that form from a verb expressing the result of an action:

1) **-ura** (*tura, sura, xura*) curvatum, curvat-**ura**– bend, curvature; fractum, fract-**ura**– break, fracture; sutum, sut-**ura** –suture, seam; fissum, fiss-**ura**-crack, fissure; comisum, commiss-**ura**– commission; junctum, junct-**ura**–to bind, juncture; incisum, incis-**ura** - to cut, tenderloin, etc.

IV. Suffixes of adjectives derived from a noun:

1) **-os** (*us, a, um*) squama, squam-**osus**-scales, scaly; fibra, fibr-**osus** – fiber, fibrous; infectio, infecti-**osus** - infection, infectious; cavern, cavern-**osus** – cave, cavernous, porous; spina, spin-**osus** – awn, spinous, arteria, arteri-**osus** - arterial; vena, ven-**osus** - venous; nervus, nerv-**osus**- nervous; villus, vill-**osus** – villous; aqua, aqu-**osus** - aqueous, aquatic; lamella, lamell-**osus** – lamellar; cribrum, cribr-**osus** - latticed, ethmoid; etc.

2) **-ar** (*is, e*) clavicula, clavicul-**aris** – clavicular; mandibula, mandibul-**aris** – mandibular; pulmo, scapula, scapula-**aris**- scapular; supecilium, supercili-**aris** – brow; jugum, jugul-**aris** – jugular; musculus, muscul-**aris** - muscular;

3) **-al** (*is, e*) vesica, vesic-**alis** -vesicular; pulmo, pulmon-**alis** – pulmonary, pulmonic; cranium, crani-**alis** – cranial; natura, natur-**alis** – natural; cortex, cortic-**alis** – cortical;

4) **-ac** (*us, a, um*) cardio, cardi-**acus** – cardiac; ilium, ili-**acus** – iliac;

3) **-ic** (*us, a, um*) thorax, thorac-**icus** – thorax, thoracic; zygoma, zygomat-**icus** - cheekbone, zygomatic; gaster, gastr-**icus** - stomach, gastric; pubes, pub-**icus** - pubic; trauma, traumat-**icus** – traumatic; tragus, trag-**icus** – tragus; thymus, thym-**icus** - thymic; ischium, ischiad-**icus** - sciatic;

4) **-in** (*us, a, um*) palatum, palat-**inus** - palate, palatal; uterus, uter-**inus**- uterus, uterine; pons, pont-**inus** – relating to the bridge;

5) **-e** (*us, a, um*) oesophagus, oesophag-**eus** - esophagus, esophageal; os, oss-**eus**- bone, bony, osseous; perone, peron-**eus** - small tibia; larynx, laryng-**eus** - larynx, laryngeal; pharynx, pharyng – **eus** - pharyngeal; triticum, tritic-**eus** – granular; tendo, tendin-**eus** – tendinous; coccyx, coccyg-**eus** – coccygeal;

V. Adverbs forming an adjective from a noun meaning similarity:

1) **-ide** (*us, a, um*) rhombos, rhombo-**ideus** - rhombus, rhomboid; delta, delto-**ideus** - deltoid; pterygo, pterygo-**ideus** -pterygo-id, wing-shaped; xypho, xypho-**ideus**–sword, xiphoid; thyro – thyro-**ideus** – shield, thyroid; stylo, stylo-**ideus** - awl, awl-shaped, trapezium, trapezo-**ideus** – trapezoidal; lambda, lambdo-**ideus** - lambdoid;

2) **-form** (*is, e*) crux, cruci – **formis** - cross, cruciform; pisum, pisi – **formis** - pea, pea-shaped; pirum, piri – **formis** - pear, pear-shaped, lens, lenti-**formis** – lenticular; etc.

3) **-at** (*us, a, um*) arcus, arcu-**atus** – arc, arc-shaped; luna, lun-**atus** - moon, semilunar; plica, plic-**atus** – plicate; stella, stell-**atus** - star-shaped;

VI. An adjective forming a suffix from a noun meaning a carrier:

-fer –(**a, um**) semen, semini-**fer** -seed, seminal; sudor, sudori – **fer** - sweat, sweaty;

VI. Suffixes of adjectives derived from numerals:

1)– **ri** (*us, a, um*) prima, prima-**rius** - primary; secunda, secunda-**rius** – secondary; tertia, tertia-**rius** – trigeminal;

VII. An adverb forming an adjective from a noun meaning a derivative, origin:

-gen (*us, a, um*) cancer, cancro – **genus** – cancer, causing cancer; pyo, pyo –**genus** – pus, causing pus, etc

At a **conclusion**, suffixes play an important role in the process of word-formation. The process of its formation is complex and multifaceted. The current stage of term formations orderly and standardized. Terms are monosemantic, that is why there is a need for a multifaceted study of medical terms. We can say that Latin suffixes increase the vocabulary of the Latin language, since they are added to the root of the word and acquire a new meaning. The suffixes indicate the type or place of occupation, action or result of action, give the term a diminutive meaning, form words that mean similarity, carrier, tools, occupation and indicate the quality or abstract concept.

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